

Research questionnaire for Schools using Academic Bridge, SaaS, as a school data management system

Dear respondents,

My name is **Martin Kanamugire**, a master's student at INES Ruhengeri. I am doing a **master's in entrepreneurship development and management**. For partial fulfilment of my master's, I am conducting research on software as a service business-related topics under the topic *"The Effects of User-Centric Approach (UCA) on Customer Acquisition, Retention, and Satisfaction (CARS) for a Software as a Service (SaaS) Start-up in Rwanda."* I request your cooperation in answering the following questions.

The study is only for academic purposes and is part of the requirements that will enable me to complete our degree program. Please be assured that the information from this research will remain confidential.

SECTION A: GENERAL INFORMATION AND INSTITUTIONAL PROFILE

Q.1: Age (Years) of respondent * *(Mark only one oval).*

- Under 20
- 21-35
- 35 – 50
- Above 50

Q.2: Gender * *Mark only one oval.*

- Male
- Female

Q.3: Marital Status *Mark only one oval.*

- Single
- Married
- Divorced/Separated
- Widow(er)

Q.4: Level of Education * *Mark only one oval.*

- Senior 6
- Bachelors' degree or Professional/TVET
- Masters' degree
- PhD level

Q.5: Type of Institution * *Mark only one oval.*

- Public
- Private
- International

Q.6: Level of Education Provided * *Mark only one oval.*

- Nursery and Primary
- Secondary
- Technical/Professional
- University

Q.7: Duration of Academic Bridge Use * *Mark only one oval.*

- less than one year 1–3
- years
- More than 3 years

SECTION B: THE EFFECTS OF USER-CENTRIC APPROACH ON CUSTOMER ACQUISITION, RETENTION AND SATISFACTION

Kindly respond with the response that matches your opinion. Please choose your appropriate option. These will be on a Likert scale ranging from Strongly agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, up to strongly disagree.

User Research (UR)

This section checks whether Academic Bridge conducts user research for initial design and improvements

Q. 8: Academic Bridge involves us, as users when designing or updating * *features. Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q.9: Involving us as users in designing and updating the system as well as *
considering our feedback retains us to use the service *Mark only one oval.*

Strongly agree

Agree

Neutral

Disagree

Strongly Disagree

Q. 10: The Academic Bridge platform reflects our feedback, and this satisfies* our
needs and interests. *Mark only one oval.*

Strongly agree

Agree

Neutral

Disagree

Strongly disagree

User Experience (UX)

This section evaluates the level of usability and friendliness of Academic Bridge platform

Q. 11: The Academic Bridge platform is user-friendly and easy to navigate. *
Mark only one oval.

Strongly agree

Agree

Neutral

Disagree

Strongly Disagree

Q.12: The Academic Bridge system layout and interface are intuitive and * attractive.

Mark only one oval.

strongly agree

Agree

Neutral

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Feedback Integration (FI)

This section checks whether Academic Bridge has feedback integration mechanisms

Q. 13: At Academic Bridge, feature updates are based on our suggestions* as users.

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

Q. 14: The Academic Bridge system provides clear feedback mechanisms *(e.g., forms, chat), allows us, and facilitates us to provide feedback. *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

Continuous User Support (CUS)

This section is about the Academic Bridge system and platform assessment on the level of User Support (US)

Q.15: The Academic Bridge system provides us quick support, once needed. **Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q.16: At Academic Bridge we are supported by knowledgeable and helpful* staff.

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

SECTION C: EVALUATION OF ACADEMIC BRIDGE OFFERING

This section evaluates your impression about Academic Bridge offering (services)

Customer Acquisition (CA)

This section assesses the reason of joining the Academic Bridge service

Q.17: We chose to use the Academic Bridge service because it provides what * we need and satisfies us. *Mark only one oval.*

- strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q.18: We decide to adopt and use the Academic Bridge platform and system * because it is easily accessible (on-boarding). *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly agree

Customer Retention (CR)

This section evaluates the level of your intention or plan to stay with the Academic Bridge service.

Q.19: We plan to continue using Academic Bridge long-term * *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q.20: The Academic Bridge features keep improving based on our feedback as * users. *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Customer Satisfaction (CS)

This section assesses the level of your satisfaction towards Academic Bridge service

Q.21: We are satisfied with the service we receive from the Academic Bridge * platform. *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q.22: Academic Bridge meets the evolving needs of our institution * *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

This section checks whether you have additional information about Academic Bridge to provide

- Do you have any other comments to provide?

Tick all that apply.

- Yes,
- No

- If yes, please feel free to provide it.

Thank you for your participation and ideas provided. The information received will strictly remain for the research purpose and confidential.